

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT OF TRANEXAMIC ACID ON MORTALITY IN PATIENTS WITH INTRACRANIAL HAEMORRHAGE AFTER TRAUMA

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Keywords

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ABSTRACT

In our country, there was no large-scale study on intracranial haemorrhages and their treatment. In this study, we aimed to determine the bleeding status of patients admitted to our emergency department with acute head trauma, to determine the type of bleeding, to determine the prognosis and to evaluate the efficacy of tranexamic acid as a medical treatment option. This retrospective study included patients admitted to University Faculty of Medicine Hospital Emergency Department between 1 January 2018 and 1 January 2019 with intracranial haemorrhage due to acute head trauma. All patients with intracranial haemorrhage were divided into 2 groups as tranexamic acid given and not given. The age, sex, type of haemorrhage and survival of the patients were recorded on the patient record forms. The data obtained from the patients were recorded and analysed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) version 21. A total of 456 head trauma patients were admitted to the emergency department in a one-year period and cerebral haemorrhage was detected in 148 cases. Of these cases, 69.6% (103) were male and 30% (45) were female. The mean age of the patients was 42.88 years. Subdural haematoma was the most common and most mortal type of haemorrhage in patients with cerebral haemorrhage. Seven of the cases in which tranexamic acid was used and 18 of the cases in which tranexamic acid was not used resulted in death. No significant correlation was found between tranexamic acid use and survival status ($p=0.080$). It was observed that mortality rate did not change in patients with and without tranexamic acid. There was no contraindication for the administration of tranexamic acid. It was thought that tranexamic acid should be given to all patients in whom surgical or medical treatment was planned.

INTRODUCTION

Trauma is a complex event resulting from the transfer of kinetic and chemical energy or heat energy to tissues, causing structural damage and adversely affecting human health. Multiple trauma can be defined as damage to more than one body cavity or region.¹

Traumas, which are one of the important public health problems in developing countries, are an important public health problem and one of the most important causes of mortality because they affect especially the young age group and bring material and mental losses. Trauma-induced injuries constitute 9.1% of all deaths in the world according to 2013 mortality data, and this rate is 27.7% in the 15-49 age range.² Each year, 50% of every 100.000 people who die due to trauma die due to head trauma. Only 40-50% of surviving patients with severe head trauma recover without sequelae. Head traumas constitute 20% of the admissions to hospital emergency departments. The most important cause of head trauma in adults is traffic accidents (60%), while falls (57%) take the first place in children.^{3,4} Statistics indicate that in addition to high mortality, survivors also develop physical and mental problems in the long term. The majority of trauma patients are young patients and traffic accidents interfere with their social, family and work lives; therefore, severe traumas pose serious public health problems.⁵ Deaths due to head trauma usually occur in the period before arrival to the hospital and in the minutes and hours immediately after the injuries. The prognosis of head trauma patients depends on timely and appropriate resuscitation and treatment as well as the severity of the trauma. Providing appropriate treatment to trauma patients in the early period following the injury minimises mortality.⁶ In the current approach to head trauma, the aim is to minimise death and disability by increasing the patient's quality of life.⁷ Therefore, the severity of the trauma should be determined before the hospital and patients should be transported to

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appropriate centres in terms of their severity. Early recognition of the severely injured patient and transfer to larger and better equipped trauma centres increases the chance of survival of these patients.⁸

Tranexamic acid is usually given to surgical patients to reduce bleeding and the need for blood transfusions. It has been shown to reduce the number of patients receiving blood transfusions by about one-third, reduce the volume of blood transfused and halve the need for further surgery to control bleeding in elective surgery patients. These findings raise the possibility that it may also be effective in traumatic brain injury.⁹

The aim of this study was to determine the effect of tranexamic acid on death and its clinical value in patients with traumatic brain injury who were admitted to the major trauma area of the Emergency Department of XXX University Faculty of Medicine, Department of Emergency Medicine as outpatients or brought by ambulance according to the triage practices defined in the method section.

In this study, we aimed to determine whether the administration of tranexamic acid in patients with head trauma presenting to the emergency department is associated with a decrease in mortality rate. Tranexamic acid is a drug that is debated worldwide whether it should be given in patients with haemorrhage. In recent studies, tranexamic acid has started to be given to patients with cranial haemorrhage in head trauma, regardless of the need for surgery. While we were not using tranexamic acid in our patients before the results of these studies, we started to give tranexamic acid to patients with cranial haemorrhage in traumatic head injuries with the decision taken by our clinic after these studies. We planned this study to determine the effect of tranexamic acid in reducing mortality and whether surgery is needed and to discuss the use of the drug in the light of new data in the literature.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This retrospective study, for which ethics committee approval was obtained from XXX University Faculty of Medicine Training and Research Hospital (16.01.2020- Decision no: 15), included 456 patients admitted to the emergency department with acute head trauma between 01.01.2018-01.01.2019. 308 patients were excluded because they did not meet the study criteria. Our study was completed with 148 patients.

As of 01.06.2018, tranexamic acid was started to be administered to patients with traumatic intracranial

haemorrhage in our clinic.

In this study, we aimed to investigate the effect of tranexamic acid treatment on mortality in patients with intracranial haemorrhage.

Between 01.01.2018-01.06.2018, patients with traumatic intracranial haemorrhage who were brought to the emergency department of XXX University Faculty of Medicine Health Practice and Research Hospital between 01.01.2018-01.06.2018 and patients with intracranial haemorrhage who applied between 01.06.2018-01.01.2019 and who were treated with tranexamic acid were compared.

Data about the patients were obtained retrospectively through electronic records and files filled in the emergency department. The outcomes of the patients were obtained through hospital informatic system(HIS) and mortality was obtained from Death Notification System (DNS) system.

The method of administration of tranexamic acid is 1 g IV bolus loading dose in the first 3 hours after trauma, followed by 1 g IV maintenance dose in 8 hours.

All data obtained in the study were analysed in SPSS IBM statistics version 21. The distribution of the data was performed by Kolmogrov Smirnov test. Continuous variables were expressed as mean±standard deviation and confidence intervals; median and minimum-maximum values were expressed as median and minimum-maximum values; categorical variables were expressed as number of cases (n) and frequency (%). The relationship between categorical variables was shown by Pearson's chi-square and Fisher's exact chi-square. The inclusion criteria for the study were as follows: patients admitted between 01.01.2018-01.01.2019 had cranial radiological evidence of bleeding, the age range of the patients was between 17 and 85 years, the trauma or clinical symptoms developed within the first 3 hours, computed tomography was performed and bleeding was shown, patients who were brought from an external centre by 112 and who were not given tranexamic acid were included.

Exclusion criteria were as follows; pediatric patients under 16 years of age, patients who were given tranexamic acid by an external centre within the first 3 hours, and patients with anticoagulant drug use were not included in the study. Cranial fracture was present in 47 of these patients and no intracranial lesion developed. 45 patients had a history of anticoagulant drug use.

RESULTS

148 cases were included in our study. 69.6% (103) of the cases

were male and 30.4% (45) were female. The mean age of the 148 cases was 42.88±17.93 years, the youngest age was 18 years and the oldest age was 81 years. 23.6% of all cases were operated. 22.2% of females and 24.3% of males were operated (p= 0.787). Tranexamic acid was used in 30.4% of the cases. Tranexamic acid was used in 35.6% of women and 28.2% of men. No significant difference was found in terms of gender (p=0,368).

83.1% of the cases continued to live after the trauma, but 16.9% of them died. 8.9 per cent of women and 20.4 percent of men died. Although the number of deaths was higher in men, there was no significant difference in terms of gender. (p=0,86).

The most common type of haemorrhage was SAH (subarachnoid haemorrhage) with 33.1% (49), followed by subdural haemorrhage with 30.4% (45). The least common type is contusion-related haemorrhage with 16.9% (25).

A comparative analysis of the use of tranexamic acid according to the bleeding type of the cases in our study is shown in Table 1. Tranexamic acid was used in 34.7% of SAH cases, 16.0% of contusion cases, 28.9% of subdural haematoma cases and 37.9% of epidural haematoma cases. Although tranexamic acid was used mostly in epidural haematoma cases, no significant correlation was found between the type of bleeding and the use of tranexamic acid. (p=0,295).

Table 1. Comparison of the bleeding pattern with the use of tranexamic acid
*N (Number), % (percent) ** Pearson Chi-square Test was used. SAB(sub-arachnoid haemorrhage)

Variables		Tranexamic acid				P Value**
		Used		Not used		
		N*	%	N	%	
Bleeding	SAB	17	34,7	32	65,3	0,295
Pattern	Contusion	4	16,0	21	84,0	
	Subdural Haematoma	13	28,9	32	71,1	
	Epidural Haematoma	11	37,9	18	62,1	

The analysis of the comparison of the type of haemorrhage and survival status of the cases is shown in Table 2. The highest rate of death was observed in subdural haematoma cases with 22.2%. The least number of exceptions was observed in contusion cases with 8.0%. There was no significant correlation between the type of haemorrhage and survival status. (p=0,459).

Table 2. Comparison of Type of Haemorrhage and Survival Status

Variables		Living Situation				P Value**
		Alive		Exitus		
		N*	%	N	%	
Bleeding	SAH	40	81,6	9	18,4	0,459
Pattern	Contusion	23	92,0	2	8,0	
	Subdural Haematoma	35	77,8	10	22,2	
	Epidural Haematoma	25	86,2	4	13,8	

*N (Number), % (percent) ** Pearson Chi-square Test was used.

The relationship between tranexamic acid use and survival status of the cases is analysed in Table 3. While 15.6% of the cases in which tranexamic acid was used died, 17.5% of the cases in which tranexamic acid was not used died. However, no significant relationship was found between the use of tranexamic acid and survival status. (p=0,080).

Table 3. The Relationship Between Tranexamic acid Use and Living Conditions of the Cases

Variables		Living Status				P value*
		Alive		Exitus		
		N*	%	N	%	
Tranexamic acid Usage	Yes	38	84,4	7	15,6	0,080
	No	85	82,5	18	17,5	

* Pearson Chi-square Test was used.

87.5 percent of women and 82.8 percent of men who used tranexamic acid survived. Although the frequency of survival was higher in women using tranexamic acid, no significant difference was observed in terms of gender. (p=0,674).

While 87.5% of the women who received tranexamic acid continued to live, 93.1% of the women who did not receive tranexamic acid continued to live. Although the frequency of survival was higher in women who did not receive tranexamic acid, no significant difference was observed. (p=0,527).

While the survival rate was 82.8% in males treated with tranexamic acid, the survival rate was 78.4% in males not treated with tranexamic acid. Although the frequency of survival was higher in men who used tranexamic acid compared to those who did not use tranexamic acid, no significant difference was detected. (p=0,620).

While 91.7% of the operated cases in which tranexamic acid

was used survived, 73.9% of the operated cases in which tranexamic acid was not used survived. The rate of survival was higher in cases where tranexamic acid was used, but there was no significant difference. ($p=0,380$).

The effect of tranexamic acid use on survival in non-operated cases is shown in Table 15. 87.8% of the cases with tranexamic acid and 85.0% of the cases without tranexamic acid survived. The frequency of survival was higher in cases where tranexamic acid was used, but no significant difference was observed. ($p=0,778$).

80.0 percent of the cases in which tranexamic acid was used and 71.4 percent of the cases in which tranexamic acid was not used survived. Although the frequency of survival was higher in cases with tranexamic acid, no significant difference was observed. ($p=0,584$).

DISCUSSION

Head traumas are a public health problem with a high mortality rate. In a study conducted by Collins et al. it was reported that head traumas constituted 14% of all emergency department admissions and ranked first among the patients hospitalised to neurosurgical services.¹⁰ Trauma patients admitted to 3rd level emergency departments are admitted more or less according to the location of the hospital, the approach principle of 2nd level hospitals to trauma patients and the decisions of 112 command and control centres. Chan et al. reported that acute head trauma accounted for 19% of all emergency admissions and 7.3% of these patients died.¹¹ Under 35 years of age, the most common cause of death and disability is traumatic brain injuries.¹² In another study conducted by Bhole et al. in India, it was reported that 200 patients with craniocerebral injuries were admitted to hospital in 3 years.¹³ Approximately 5.000 (5%) of 100.000 patients admitted to our hospital annually are trauma patients. Approximately 10% of these trauma patients have traumatic brain injury. This value was found to be low compared to studies conducted abroad. This may be explained by the fact that XXX University Medical Faculty Hospital is located far from the settlement centre. In endemic regions where there is war, in regions where traffic is dense and in regions where industrial branches are more dense, men are admitted to hospital due to trauma more than women. Frankowski et al. reported that head trauma was 4 times more common in men than in women.¹⁴ In the literature, it has been reported that the gender exposed to head trauma is males under the age of 40

years and that they are exposed to trauma 2-3 times more than females.^{15,16} The male sex ratio of 69.6% in our study is compatible with the literature. The current situation can be explained by the fact that men are more socially active, occupational accidents, traffic accidents and war injuries are more common in the male gender. Although head traumas are common at all ages, they are in the first class of diseases in adults according to both disability and mortality rates. In a study on the mean age of trauma patients, this value was found to be between 40.4 and 51.5 years.^{6,17} In our study, the mean age of the patients was 42.88 years, the mean age of the women was 45.76 years and the mean age of the men was 41.62 years. Adults with head trauma have a higher mortality and disability rate compared to other age groups.

It has been reported that minor head traumas constitute the majority of studies on head traumas.^{18,19} Our study started with a total of 456 patients and 10.3% were excluded because of minor head trauma. We found that our results were not compatible with the literature. This may be explained by the fact that our hospital is far from the city centre and the admission of severe head trauma cases is high.

Two types of treatment modalities, surgical and medical, are applied to patients with head trauma. In the world, certain criteria and new medical treatments are constantly discussed in terms of whether patients should be taken to surgery or not. This issue has still not been clarified. In a study of 307 cases by Yavuz et al. it was found that 84 (27%) of the patients with acute head trauma underwent surgical operation while 73% received medical treatment.²⁰ In another study of 250 cases, 127 cases were operated and 123 cases were treated medically (21). In our study, 23.6% of all cases were operated, 22.2% of women and 24.3% of men were operated. Our study supports other national studies.

Subdural haemorrhage is observed more frequently in trauma-related patients compared to other cranial haemorrhages and has a more mortal course. In a study by Yavuz et al. including 241 patients, the mortality rate was 27% and the most mortal haemorrhage was found to be subdural haematoma, and 31% of the cases were operated.²⁰ In another study, the total number of cases was 250, the mortality rate was 13.6%, 32% of these cases were operated and the most mortal haemorrhage was again subdural haematoma.²¹ In our study, 83.1% of the cases continued to live after the trauma, but 16.9% of the cases died and 23.1% of all cases were operated. In our study, the most mortal haemorrhage was subdural haematoma, which is

consistent with the literature. Compared to the study by Yavuz et al., the reason why our cases had fewer deaths can be evaluated with the need for less surgery. In previous studies, subdural haematoma was found to be the most mortal type of haemorrhage.

In our study, tranexamic acid was started to be given to all patients with intracranial haemorrhage in the emergency department of XXX University as of 01.06.2018. It was determined that the frequency of tranexamic acid use was 30.4% compared to all cases in 2018. Cases in which tranexamic acid was administered accounted for 35.6% of women and 28.2% of men. Tranexamic acid is usually given to surgical patients to reduce bleeding and the need for blood transfusion. It has been shown to reduce the number of patients receiving blood transfusion by approximately one third and to eliminate the need for further surgery to control bleeding in elective surgery patients.²² In the double-blind, placebo-controlled randomised study by Surakrant et al., intracranial haemorrhages were present in 21 (18%) of 120 patients given tranexamic acid and 32 of 118 placebo patients. The difference was not statistically significant (RR = 0.65). There was no evidence of an increased risk of thromboembolic events in patients given tranexamic acid.²³ In our study, the relationship between the use of tranexamic acid and the survival status of the cases showed that 15.6% of the cases in which tranexamic acid was used died, whereas 17.5% of the cases in which tranexamic acid was not used died. However, no significant relationship was found between the use of tranexamic acid and survival status of the cases. In both studies, it was determined that the mortality rate decreased with the use of tranexamic acid, but no significant difference was obtained.

When we controlled for gender in the patients who received tranexamic acid, 17.2% of men and 12.5% of women died. The reason for the higher number of males may be the higher number of multiple traumas associated with head trauma.

When the effect of tranexamic acid use on survival status was analysed only among women, 87.5% of women who used tranexamic acid continued to live, while 93% of women who did not use tranexamic acid continued to live. Although the survival rate of women who did not use tranexamic acid was higher, no significant difference was observed. When we looked at the relationship between tranexamic acid use and survival status of men, it was found that the survival rate of those who used tranexamic acid was 82.8%, while the survival

rate of patients who were not given tranexamic acid as treatment was 78.4%. Although it was observed that tranexamic acid decreased the mortality rate, no significant difference was detected. It can be said that tranexamic acid is more effective in males than females.

Tranexamic acid has been shown in many studies to reduce the need for transfusion during operation and to prevent haemorrhagic shock in patients. While 91.7% of the patients who were operated and tranexamic acid was used survived, 73.9% of the patients who were operated without tranexamic acid survived. The survival rate was higher in the cases operated on with tranexamic acid, but no significant difference was found. Since bleeding in isolated head traumas is usually self-limiting, spinal shock is seen with spinal shock as a result of shifting and pons compression rather than haemorrhagic shock due to bleeding. Mortality rates were decreased with the use of tranexamic acid in patients operated for head trauma, but statistical significance was not found.

The effect of tranexamic acid use on survival in non-operated cases was 87% of the cases continued to live, while the rate was 85% in cases without tranexamic acid use. The survival rate was higher in cases where tranexamic acid was used, but no significant difference was found. There is no study on this subject in the international and national literature and a large series of cases in which both operation was not considered and tranexamic acid was given and followed up are needed.

In patients over 65 years of age, 80% of the cases survived when tranexamic acid was used and 71.4% of the cases without tranexamic acid. The use of tranexamic acid in patients over 65 years of age has not been studied nationally and internationally as over 65 years of age, these patients have been considered as the general population of patients with cranial haemorrhage and studies have been conducted in this direction. In our study, we wanted to study patients over 65 years of age separately because they have comorbidities and the body's ability to recover is less than in younger patients.

Although there was no significant decrease in the mortality rate in cranial haemorrhage after tranexamic acid was given to these patients, as stated in the American trauma guideline, it is considered appropriate to give tranexamic acid to patients because it will not cause any side effects and in our study, we think that tranexamic acid should be given to patients over 65 years of age because it has no side effects. There is a need for review studies that are larger and include trauma hospitals.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it was observed that the decrease in mortality in patients with intracranial haemorrhage due to trauma given tranexamic acid was not statistically valuable, but it decreased the shock duration of the patients and contributed to the stability of the patients until surgery was performed. When tranexamic acid administered and not administered patients were compared, the absence of a condition affecting mortality due to the side effect of tranexamic acid does not constitute a contraindication for the use of tranexamic acid in these patients. It was determined that the mortality rate decreased with the use of tranexamic acid in trauma patients, but no significant difference was obtained. Since there is no reason to increase mortality due to tranexamic acid in patients given tranexamic acid, we think that it is correct to give tranexamic acid to patients.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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No

REFERENCES

- Karakuş A, Kecec Z, Akcan R, et al. The relationship of travma severity and mortality with cardiac enzymes and cytokines at multipl travma patients. *Ulus travma Acil Cerrahi Derg*, 2012;18 (4):289–295
- Battistella FD, Benfield JR. Blunt and penetrating injüries of the chest wall, pleura and lungs. In: Shield Tw. *General thoracic surgery*. 5nd Ed. Philadelphia: Williams and wilkins, 2000:815–863.
- Mirzai H, Yađlı N, Tekin İ. Celal Bayar Üniversitesi Tıp Fakültesi acil birimine başvuran kafa travmalı olguların epidemiyolojik ve klinik özellikleri. *Ulusal Travma Dergisi*. 2005;2:146 – 152
- Bulut M, Korkmaz A, Akköse Ş, Balcı V, Özgüç H, Tokyay R. Çocukluk Çağındaki Düşmelerin Epidemiyolojik Ve Klinik Özellikleri. *Ulusal Travma Dergisi*. 2002;4:20 – 223
- Chawda MN, Hildebrand F, Pape HC, Giannoudis PV. Predicting outcome after multiple trauma: which scoring system? *Injury*. 2004 Apr; 35(4):347–58.
- Rahmani F, Ebrahimi Bakhtavar H, Shams Vahdati S, Hosseini M, Mehdizadeh Esfanjani R. Evaluation of MGAP and GAP Trauma Scores to Predict Prognosis of Multiple-trauma Patients. *Trauma Monthly*. Kowsar; 2016 Jun 12; In press.
- Stoica B, Paun S, Tanase I, Negoii I, Chiotoroii A, Beuran M, et al. Probability of Survival Scores in Different Trauma Registries: A Systematic Review. *Chirurgia (Bucur)*. 2016 Mar;111(2):115–9.
- Llompert-Pou JA, Chico-Fernández M, Sánchez-Casado M, SalaberriaUdabe R, Carbayo-Górriz C, Guerrero-López F, et al. Scoring severity in trauma: comparison of prehospital scoring systems in trauma ICU patients. *Eur J Trauma Emerg Surg*. 2016 Apr 18:1–7.
- Perel P, Al-Shahi Salman R, Kawahara T, Morris Z, Prieto-Merino D. CRASH-2 (Clinical Randomisation of an Antifibrinolytic in Significant Haemorrhage) intracranial bleeding study: the effect of tranexamic acid in traumatic brain injury - a nested randomised, placebo-controlled trial. *Health Technol Assess* 2012;16(13)
- Collins JG: Types of injuries by selected characteristics: United States, 1985-1987. *Vital Health Statistics* 1990;10:175.
- Chan BS, Walker PJ, Cass DT. Urban trauma: an analysis of 1116 paediatric cases. *J Trauma* 1989;29:1540–7.
- Paşaođlu A. Erişkinde Kafa Travmaları. *Temel Nöroşürürji Cilt I, Türk Nöroşürürji Derneđi Yayınları*, S.316-323: 2005 Ankara.
- Bhole AM, Potode R, Agrawal A, Joharapurkar SR. Demographic Profile, Clinical Presentation, Management Options In Cranio-Cerebral Trauma: An Experience Of A Rural Hospital in Central India. *Pak J Med Sci* 2007;23:724-727.
- Frankowski RF, Annegers JF, Whitman S. Epidemiological and descriptive studies. *National Institute of Health*. 1985;45:33-51.
- Langlois JA, Rutland-Brown W, Wald MM. The epidemiology and impact of traumatic brain injury: a brief overview. *J Head Trauma Rehabil*. 2006; 5: 375-8.
- Işık HS, Bostancı U, Yıldız Ö, Özdemir C, Gökyar A. Kafa travması nedeniyle tedavi edilen 954 erişkin olgunun retrospektif deđerlendirilmesi: Epidemiyolojik çalışma. *Ulus Travma Acil Cerrahi Dergisi*. 2011;1:46-7.
- Kondo Y, Abe T, Kohshi K, Tokuda Y, Cook EF, Kukita I. Revised trauma scoring system to predict in-hospital mortality in the emergency department: Glasgow Coma Scale, Age, and Systolic Blood Pressure score. *Critical Care*. *BioMed Central Ltd*; 2011 Aug 10;15(4):R191.
- Mohanty SK, Thompson W, Rakower S. Are CT scans for head injury patients always necessary? *J Trauma* 1991; 31:801-805.
- Stein SC, Ross SE. The value of computed tomographic scans patients with low-risk head injuries. *Neurosurgery*. 1990;4:638-640.
- Yavuz O, Ahmet B, et al. Retrospective analysis of patients with acut head trauma in our emergency service treatise no: 229801
- İbrahim M Ziyal, Bülent F Kılınçođlu, Yunus Aydın. Intracranial bleeding due to trauma. *Ulus Travma Acil Cerrahi Derg*. 1998; 4(3): 193-196
- Dewan, Y, Komolafe, E.O, Mejía-Mantilla, J.H. et al. CRASH-3 - tranexamic acid for the treatment of significant traumatic brain injury: study protocol for an international randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Trials* 13, 87 2012
- Surakrant Y, Warawut K, Parnumas P et al. Tranexamic acid for patients with traumatic brain injury: A randomized double-blinded, placebo-controlled trial 2013